

after inoculation, seedlings were indexed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay.

No line showed visible symptoms of RTV. All lines were resistant to RTSV; RTBV infection varied from 40 to 85% (see table). Ratakita 1, RAUSRR15, and TCA227 had no RTBV + RTSV infection. Varieties resistant to GLH were predominantly infected with RTBV alone.

Crosses made to incorporate resistance to GLH and RTV can serve as new sources of resistance. ■

Reaction of selected rice lines from Bihar, India, to GLH, RTBV, and RTSV. IRRI, 1987.

Line	Plants tested (no.)	GLH reaction ^a	Infection ^b (%)	
			RTBV + RTSV	RTBV
Ratakita 1	53	1	0.0	45.3
RAUSRR15	42	3	0.0	76.2
RAUSRR18	54	3	1.4	42.6
TCA4-1	35	3	8.5	40.0
TCA227	41	3	0.0	85.4
TCA269	20	3	30.0	40.0

^aNo-choice test. ^bAll lines had zero RTSV infection. Standard evaluation system for rice scale 1 to 9. Susceptible TN1 scored 9; resistant IR29 scored 3.

Detection of tungro viruses after inoculation

Z. M. Flores, E. R. Tiongco, R. C. Cabunagan, and H. Koganezawa, IRRI

We examined how soon rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical viruses (RTSV) can be detected by enzyme-

linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Adult green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* were given 3 d acquisition feeding on TN1 Plants infected with both RTBV and RTSV or with RTSV alone and introduced on 21-d-old TN1 seedlings in the greenhouse at 1 or 5 insects/seedling for 24-h inoculation (90 seedlings inoculated with each virus source

with a given number of leafhoppers).

Leaves 10-15 mm long were sampled daily to 7 d after inoculation (DAI) and at 12 and 18 DAI.

Initial detection of RTBV was at 3 DAI. At 4 DAI, the number of plants in which both viruses were newly detected increased sharply, then gradually decreased thereafter (see figure).

RTSV alone was initially detected 4 DAI in seedlings inoculated by 5 leafhoppers and 5 DAI in seedlings inoculated with 1 leafhopper. Maximum detection of RTSV was 7-12 DAI.

These results indicate that multiplication of RTSV alone is slower than when plants are infected with both viruses. ■

Detection of RTSV alone, RTBV alone, and RTBV + RTSV in 21-d-old TN1 seedlings inoculated 1 or 5 *Nephotettix virescens* in the greenhouse. Bars below the base line show percentage of plants in which RTBV or RTSV was detected first as single infection, then as double infection.

Upland rice genotypes resistant to blast (BI) disease in West Sumatra

J. Castano, B. Amril, D. Syahril, and Z. Zaini, Sukarami Research Institute for Food Crops, P.O. Box 34, Padang, West Sumatra, Indonesia

In 1987, we developed a method for screening B1 resistance in the field and evaluated 437 upland rice genotypes from Indonesia, CIAT (Colombia), EMBRAPA (Brazil), and IRRI (Philippines) six times within 2 yr. Under heavy disease pressure, 176 showed a high degree of resistance (see table). Many of them showed attributes of slow susceptibility under epiphytotic conditions in the field.

The materials are being used in our upland rice breeding program to improve the B1 resistance of local cultivars. ■

Origin	Entries (no.)	Genotypes (no.) with given disease rating ^a		
		R (1-5%)	I (6-25%)	S (>25 %)
CIAT, Colombia	198	126	38	34
EMBRAPA, Brazil	16	15	1	0
Indonesia	91	0	10	81
IRRI, Philippines	132	35	64	33
Total	437	176	113	148

Local checks:
C22 (S): 100% dead
Danau Laut Tawar (R): 3, 4 (25%)

^a Disease severities evaluated according to disease damage index keys to estimate damage caused by major diseases of upland rice. R = resistant, I = intermediate, S = susceptible.

Pest resistance — insects

Evaluation of rice cultivars for resistance to leafhopper (LF)

J. B. Tomar, S. C. Prasad, M. P. Singh, and S. D. Tomar, Plant Breeding and Genetics Department, Birsa Agricultural University, Kanke, Ranchi 834006, India (present address: NBPGR Regional Station, Hinoo House, Hinoo, Ranchi 834002, India)

We screened 81 rice cultivars from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, for LF resistance 1986-87.

Entries were direct seeded in 4 × 1.05-m plots with two replications. Recommended agronomic practices were followed.

LF infestation was heavy 70 d after sowing, when the crop was in the booting to flowering stage. Susceptible check Brown gora had 90% infestation. Damaged and undamaged leaves of each test entry were counted in 1 m² of each replication, and averages calculated. Percentage damaged leaves was converted into 0-9 point scale:

$$\text{Scale} = \frac{\% \text{ damaged leaves in test cultivar}}{\% \text{ damaged leaves in susceptible check}}$$

In 1986, RP1714-111-7-3-2 and OR811-2 had no LF damage. In 1987, RD2599-150-18-8-5 and RAU156-56 had no damage.

Reactions of most cultivars changed in 1987. RP1714-111-7-3-2 and OR811-2, which had 0 damage in 1986, were evaluated at 3 in 1987.

Cultivars that scored 0, 1, and 3 both years could be treated as resistant and used in a crossing program (see table). ■

Cultivars that scored 0-3 for LF resistance. Ranchi, India, 1986 and 1987.

Score	Cultivars
	<i>1986</i>
0	RP1714-111-7-3-2, OR811-2
1	RP2217-71-73-14, RP2525-19-124, RP1888-132-24-11-8, RP2522-16-14-80, NDR119, UPR83-28, UPR83-20, NDK224, NDR222, BG367-4, and CN747-1-4
3	RP2415-203-5-1-2, RP2263-934-592-5, RP2235-35-40-50, RTN500, RP2423-5-77-16, TNAU301790, Akashi, TNAU81804, NRL502, TNAU83134, TNAU83108, NDR312-1, NR571-1, MAUSEL 10, RP2601-24-36-138, Pusa 510, JR35, OR811-10, RP2599-150-18-8-5, ADT85001, RAU151-56
	<i>1987</i>
0	RP2599-150-188-8-5, RAU151-56
1	OR811-10, ADT85001, RP2522-16-14-80, NDR119, UPR83-28, TNAU83108
3	RP1714-111-7-3-2, OR811-2, RP2217-71-73-14, RP2525-19-124, RP1888-132-24-11-8, UPR83-20, NDR224, NDR222, BG367-4, CN747-1-4, RP2415-203-5-1-2, RP2263-934-592-5, RTN500, RP2423-5-77-16, Akashi, Pusa 510, RAU4071-51-13, RAU4045-2A.

Stress tolerance — excess water

Inheritance of submergence tolerance in rice

P. K. S. Ray, Plant Breeding Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh; D. HilleRis-Lambers, IRRI; and N. M. Tepora, Central Luzon State University, Philippines

We traced inheritance of submergence tolerance in six submergence-tolerant advanced lines crossed with susceptible IR11288-B-B-69-1. Seeds of the parents, F₁, and F₂ were sown in 5 × 5-cm plastic pots and placed in galvanized iron trays in the glasshouse. Seedlings were pulled 35 d after sowing and tillers separated to test submergence tolerance. At 10 d after separation, trays containing potted tillers were put in a tank inside the greenhouse and the plants submerged to 90 cm for 12 d. Recovery was measured 7 d after submergence.

Submergence tolerance of the F₁ and F₂ was calculated by dividing their survival by the survival percentage of the tolerant parent.

Survival in the F₁ of four crosses tended toward the tolerant parent; survival in two crosses was very poor (see table). This implies that dominance of submergence tolerance varies.

Although survival of the F₁ of BKNFR76106-16-0-1/IR11288 was very poor, the F₂ showed tolerance (which was expected). The reason for the discrepancy in the F₁ is not clear.

Survival was higher in crosses involving strongly submergence-tolerant parents that derive their tolerance from FR13A or Kurkaruppan (BKNFR76106-13-2 and IR29012-4-1-3 from FR13A and IR31406-333-1 from Kurkaruppan). Survival was lower in the crosses involving moderately tolerant parents IR21567-16-2-2 and IR8234-OT-9-2 (they presumably obtained their genes for tolerance from moderately tolerant KLG6986 and Nam Sagui 19).